

A Geographical Study of Soil Types and Distribution of Settlement in Solapur District

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Abstract:-

There are many important physical factors which are influencing the distribution of settlement are relief, availability of water, climate, soil, rainfall, availability of cultivated land etc. "Settlement geography is a science of systematic inquiry of occupancy features distributed over space with differentiation in relation to man" (Mandal, 1970). Settlement responds to man's environment as well as the religious and social customs of the society. Rural settlements are the important aspect of settlement and human geography, as they reflect the complex relationship of human occupation to land and environment.

The study of settlement is basic to human geography, because the form of settlement in any region reflects men's relationship with the environment. The settlement distribution is not only determined by the natural condition but other several factors also influence the distribution of settlements such as physiography, drainage pattern, population and other **several** factors. The settlement is a basic administrative unit. The settlements with number of clusters or hamlets are divided from each other by parcel of agricultural or other land activities within a particular territorial unit. Settlement as an occupancy unit, represents the organized colony of human beings including the building in which they live or work or store their material. It also includes tracks or streets over which their mobility takes place.

Rural settlements are primary settlement and it is related to primary economic activity. According to Stone (1965) "Rural settlement geography is the description and analysis of the distribution of building by which people attach themselves to the land for the purpose of primary production." The people living in rural settlement are mainly engaged in agriculture, fishing, rearing animals, mining and forestry. The rural settlement is made by local a material that is woods, vegetable matter, mud and stone. The natural environment affects the characteristics of the settlement in a particular region. Settlements are considered as an index of human adjustment to the environment.

The present research papers as an attempt to study soil types and distribution of settlement in Solapur district. For that study rural settlement in period 2011 has been taken into the consideration. The present study is mainly based on the secondary data which is collected from the Census Handbook of Solapur District and Socio-Economic Abstract of Solapur district.

Keywords: - Rural Settlement, Soil Types, Settlement Distribution,

1. Introduction:-

India is a rural country, where about two-third population of the total is still living in rural areas and only one-third population of the total resides in the urban areas. According to R.B. Singh (1969), the term settlement refers to the humanisation of the natural landscape by man, but settlement geography is generally defined as cluster of houses including the surrounding lands usually grouped at a convenient site and generally without any formal plan. The settlement geography studies the spatial relationship between the land and settlement. The term settlement is frequently used, but it is very difficult to define it. In simple terms, we can define a settlement as any form of human habitation that extends

from a settlement to a large city called a settlement.

Settlement geography is a part of the social aspect of human geography. Villages, towns and cities built by man recreate the environment and change the relationship between the inhabitants and their environment. "Settlement geography is the study of the form of the cultural landscape" (Jordan-1966). Rural settlements include populated areas whose inhabitants are engaged primarily in agriculture, forestry, or hunting. Rural settlements are primary settlement and it is related to primary economic activity. The people living in rural settlement mainly engaged in agriculture, fishing, rearing animals, mining and forestry. The rural settlement made by

local materials that is woods, vegetable matter, mud and stone. The function of rural settlement has been also different.

The term settlement is very frequently used, but when it comes for defining, it is very difficult to give a clear cut definition. In simpler term we can define settlement as any form of human habitation which ranges from a single dwelling to large city called as a settlement. The word settlement has another connotation as well as this is a process of opening up and settling of a previously uninhabited area by the people. In geography this process is also known as occupancy. Therefore, we can say settlement is a process of grouping of people as well as acquiring of some territory to build houses as well as for their economic support. It has been observed

2. Study Area:-

Solapur district is one of the important districts in Maharashtra. It lies entirely in the Bhima-Sina-Man basins. The district of Solapur is located between 17° 10' North and 18° 32' North latitudes and 74° 42' East and 76° 15' East longitudes. The East-West Length of the district is about 200 kilometer and North-South width is about 150 kilometer. The total geographical area of the Solapur district is about 14895 square kilometer and population is 43,17,756 according to 2011 census. In term of area, Karmala is the largest tahsil and the lowest is North Solapur tahsil in the Solapur district. Solapur district plays significant role in the fields of agriculture, economics, industrial and social fields. The present paper deals with the study soil types and settlement distribution in Solapur district.

3. Objectives:-

The important objectives of the present paper are as follows

To study the soil types and distribution of settlement in Solapur district.

4. Database And Methodology:-

The present paper depends on the secondary data. It has been collected through District Census Handbook, Social Economic Review and other materials used. The study has been concentrated in the impact of physiography on settlement distribution in Solapur district. Some other sources of information are used for the present research, like unpublished material.

The collected information from the different sources is processed and percentage calculated. Final results are presented in the

that various factors affected the settlement distribution. The main factors responsible for the distribution of settlement are physical, socio-cultural and economical. But it has been observed that the physical factors are strongly responsible for the distribution of the settlement. In this physical factor such as physiography, soil, drainage is the important factors. According to R.L.Singh (1975), "The term villages means group of dwellings which may be compact, semi-compact or hamleted, clustered and linear emerging as a result of interplay of physical and cultural factors." The present paper is an attempt to study the soil types and the distribution of rural settlement. According to 2011 census, it has been observed that there are 1154 rural settlements in the Solapur district.

form of tables with help of these tables different diagrams, graphs are made and analyzed.

5. Rural Settlement in the Solapur District:-

Rural settlement is the basic factor of geographic study. Table -1 shows the rural settlement in the Solapur district. Table 1 exhibit that the total number of settlements in the entire study area is 1154. But it varies from tahsil to tahsil, the highest number of rural settlement has been shown in the Akkalkot tahsil that is 140, while the lowest rural settlement has been shown in the North Solapur tahsil that is 41.

Table No- 1
Rural Settlement in the Solapur District (2011)

SR. No.	Name of Tahsil	Number of Rural Settlements
1	Karmala	123
2	Madha	117
3	Barshi	139
4	North Solapur	41
5	Mohol	104
6	Pandharpur	102
7	Malshiras	114
8	Sangola	102
9	Mangalwedha	81
10	South Solapur	91
11	Akkalkot	140
	District Total	1154

Source: Compiled by the researcher based on District census handbook 2011.

6. Soil Types And Distribution Of Settlement:-

The soil types and distribution of settlements is closely related to each other. The soil quality is directly affecting the distribution of the settlement in the particular region. It has been also seen that

good quality fertile soil has large number of settlements, while the unfertile soil has less number of the settlements.

The following table shows the different types of soil and distribution of the settlements.

Table No- 2
Soil Types and Distribution of Settlement

Sr. No.	Soil Types	No of Settlements	Percentage of Settlement
1	Shallow Gray	155	13.43
2	Medium Black	652	56.49
3	Black	347	30.06
	Total	1154	100

Source: Computed by researcher

Fig. 2

The highest percentage of settlement is found in the medium black soil which is 56 percent, because this soil type is ideal for the settlement development. The lowest settlement has been seen in the shallow gray type which is only 13 percent, because it is

not favorable for the settlement development. The moderate settlement has been seen in the black soil because this soil is good for agricultural practices hence settlement moderate numbers of settlements have been found in this category.

Fig. 3

8. Distribution Of Settlement According To Soil Types:-

There are three categories of settlement distribution according to soil types, they are as under:

a) Shallow Gray Soil and Distribution of Settlement (Low Settlement Distribution):-

The total number of settlements included in this category in the study area is 155. The percentage found is 13.43 percent. The lowest settlement has been seen in the shallow gray soil type, because it is not favorable for the settlement development.

b) Medium Black Soil and Distribution of Settlement (High Settlement Distribution):-

The total number of settlements in this category in Solapur district is 652. The highest percentage of settlement is found in the medium black soil which is 56.49 percent, because this soil type is ideal for the settlement development.

c) Black Soil and Distribution of Settlement (Moderate Settlement Distribution) :-

The total number of settlements in this category is found 347. The number of percentage in this category is 30.06 percent settlement. The moderate settlement has been seen in the black soil because this soil is good for agricultural practices hence settlement moderate numbers of settlements have been found in this category.

9. Conclusion:-

It has been seen that many factors related to physical, socio-economic and cultural factors affect the settlement distribution in the study area. Physical factors such as physiography, soil types and other physical factors have been mainly responsible for distribution of settlement in the Solapur district.

Soils types are very dominate factors responsible for distribution of settlement in the Solapur district. The highest percentage of settlement is found in the medium black

soil which is 56.49 percent, because this soil type is ideal for the settlement development. The moderate settlement has been seen in the black soil which is 30.06 percent, because this soil is good for agricultural practices hence settlement moderate numbers of settlements have been found in this category. The lowest settlement has been seen in the shallow gray soil type which is 13.43 percent, because it is not favorable for the settlement development.

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